

CHARACTERIZATION AND EVALUATION OF HIGH-STRENGTH LIGHTWEIGHT ABLATOR USING POROUS CARBON MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

In order to manufacture lightweight and high strength ablator, we employed a porous carbon material as a preform. Since the porous carbon material has three-dimensional network structure and uniform open-cells, it shows isotropic properties and high strength compared with other porous carbon foam. As a result, compressive strength of the newly developed ablator was 26 MPa, that was 17 times higher than that of conventional ablators using carbon fiber preforms. The strength was sustained even after carbonization, because the porous carbon preform was kept its structure. Furthermore, the recession resistance of the developed ablator in the arc wind tunnel test was equal to that of the conventional ablator. This new lightweight ablator also indicated good thermal insulation performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermal protection system (TPS) is an imperative technology for re-entry of space vehicles. An ablator is one of the TPS materials which have been used for the heat shield of re-entry vehicles. Typical examples of ablation materials are made of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP). Fig. 1 shows the thermal protection mechanism of ablators. Under re-entry environments, the ablator produces gases as the result of pyrolysis reaction of matrix, and these gases insulate influx of aerodynamic heating into inside of vehicles [1]. In addition, the pyrolysis reaction is typically endothermic. These processes act as the thermal protect mechanism.

Recently, much attention has been paid to lightweight ablators for re-entry capsules of next-generation spacecrafts. Phenolic Impregnated Carbon Ablator (PICA) developed by NASA is one of the typical lightweight ablators using the carbon fiber preform. PICA has been used for the heat shield of Stardust and Mars Science Laboratory [1, 2]. PICA has good thermal properties, but the mechanical properties are low, because it is mainly composed of short carbon fiber bound with small amount of resin and carbonaceous binders [3]. Since the binder is quite brittle, it potentially becomes a fracture origin. Furthermore, PICA has large open pores because only a small amount of the resin used to reduce the density. For these reasons, lightweight ablator using fiber preform exhibits low strength [3]. In addition, when the ablator is exposed to the high-speed gas flow like re-entry environment, bound fibers will be mechanically separated each other and then fly apart. It is the main reason for high mechanical erosion of lightweight ablator.

In this study, we focused on porous carbon material to manufacture the high-strength lightweight ablator. We also evaluated mechanical properties of the developed ablator. In addition, recession behavior under arc jet wind tunnel was also examined.

Fig. 1 Mechanisms of charring ablative materials.

2 Materials

2.1 Porous carbon material

A porous carbon material (Three dimensionally Networked Porous Carbon: TNPC) used for developed ablator has open-cell and three-dimensional network structure as shown in Fig. 2. Since the cells of TNPC have uniform distribution, TNPC shows isotropic properties. Due to these structural characteristics, TNPC also shows higher mechanical properties than those of other foams. In addition, TNPC has wide flow channels unlike typical carbon forms. This is advantage because we can impregnate with resin easily. Table 1 shows the densities and porosities of TNPCs. The cell size of TNPC 1, 2, and 3 were 7.2, 9.9 and 16.0 μm , respectively. The bulk densities were in the range from 0.36 to 0.38 g/cm^3 and the porosities were in the range of 70 ~ 80 % in all cell size.

Fig. 2 Microstructure of various cell size of TNPC. The Cell size is (a) 7.2 μm , (b) 9.9 μm and (c) 16.0 μm .

Table 1 The material properties of TNPCs.

	TNPC 1	TNPC 2	TNPC 3
Bulk density (g/cm^3)	0.374	0.369	0.376
Pore diameter (μm)	7.2	9.9	16
Porosity (%)	79.7	80.0	77.2

2.1 Fabrication process of Porous Carbon Ablator

Fig. 3 shows the fabrication procedure of the developed ablator (Porous Carbon Ablator: PCA). The polyamic-acid was dissolved in Dimethylacetamide (DMAc), where the concentration of polyamic-acid was set to 15 wt%. TNPC soaked in this solution was kept in vacuum (0 MPa) for 3 hours. And then, vacuum and pressure impregnations at 0 MPa and 0.4 MPa were repeated 3 or 4 times. After the impregnation, the resin was dried and cured by heating from room temperature to 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a vacuum oven. The density of PCAs was 0.48 g/cm^3 in any cell size. These PCAs were denoted as PCA 1, PCA 2 and PCA 3, as in the case of TNPC.

Fig. 3 Fabrication procedure of PCA.

3 Experimental

3.1 Compressive test

The compressive strength of TNPC, PCA and charred-PCA was evaluated. PCA was heat treated at 950 °C in Ar atmosphere to obtain charred-PCA specimens. The specimen geometry was 10×10×20 mm. In this test, the specimen was compressed along longitudinal direction. The test was carried out using a screw driven testing machine (INSTRON 5067). Uniaxial compressive load was applied with the cross-head speed of 0.1 mm/min. Thin PTFE sheet was put between jig and specimen to reduce friction.

3.2 Arc-jet wind tunnel Test

Fig. 4 shows shape and geometries of specimens used in the arc-jet wind tunnel test. The specimens were covered by the bakelite holder and glass fiber cloth to prevent heating on the side surface. As shown in Table 2, the tests were carried out under the three different heating conditions of 1.8, 3.2 and 6.0 MW/m². The heating time was set to 30 seconds in all tests. During experiments, the heated surface temperature was measured by a radiation thermometer. The emissivity of 0.85 was applied for developed ablator, and 0.9 for the TNPC preform. The K-type thermocouples were located at the 20 and 30 mm depth from the heated surface to monitor internal temperature. After the tests, the recession length at the stagnation point was measured by a scanning laser displacement sensor (LK-G155, KEYENCE).

Fig. 4 The specimen geometry for Arc-jet wind tunnel test.

Table 2 Specimens and testing conditions.

Test Conditions	A	B	C
Specimen diameter (mm)	50	50	50
Heat flux (MW/m ²)	1.8	3.2	6
Stagnation pressure (kPa)	4.6	13.0	19.7
Flow enthalpy (MJ/kg)		14	
Heating time (sec.)	30	30	30

4 Result

4.1 Compressive test

Fig. 5 shows a typical stress-strain curve of each specimen. The crack initiated and grew in the plateau region as shown in the figure. Microstructural observation revealed that the columns of the cell were fractured during cracking. This is typical behavior of open-cell structures [4].

In this study, the compressive strength was defined as the maximum compressive stress support by the specimen, and the corresponding strain was regarded as the fracture strain as with the test of PICA [5]. Table 3 shows the compressive properties of each PCA. Maximum compressive strength of PCA was 25.7 MPa. This value is 17 times higher than that of PICA in the in-plane direction. In addition, the strength of Virgin PCA was equal to Charred PCA.

4.2 Arc-jet wind tunnel test

4.2.1 Surface and internal temperature

Fig. 6 shows the surface temperature during the arc-jet wind tunnel tests. The surface temperature of PCA was lower than that of TNPC at least within 10 seconds from the beginning. This is caused by thermal insulation of pyrolysis gases, called blocking effect. In addition, the difference of surface temperature between PCA and TNPC was larger in the test of higher heating rate. The developed ablator also indicates thermal insulation performance. Table 4 shows the maximum surface and internal temperature of the each specimen. Although the maximum surface temperature was over 2000 °C, the internal temperature was in the range of 200 to 300 °C at 20 mm depth and about 170 °C at 30 mm depth.

Fig. 5 The typical stress-strain curve of specimens.

Table 3 Compressive properties of ablation materials.

Material	Direction	Density (g/cm ³)		Compressive strength (MPa)		Compressive modulus (GPa)		Fracture strain (%)	
		Virgin	Charred	Virgin	Charred	Virgin	Charred	Virgin	Charred
TNPC1	Isotropy	0.387		14.0		1.32		2.46	
TNPC2		0.388		14.7		1.39		2.62	
TNPC3		0.387		26.9		2.18		2.28	
Carbon fiber preform of PICA[5]	In-plane	0.187		0.81		0.057		4.10	
	Out-of plane	0.185		1.01		0.014		58.0	
PCA1	Isotropy	0.480	0.413	20.2	20.7	1.86	2.61	2.50	2.27
PCA2		0.488	0.429	21.7	22.8	2.08	2.86	2.53	1.88
PCA3		0.478	0.427	25.7	24.4	2.53	3.18	2.51	2.27
PICA[5]	In-plane	0.220	0.225	1.55	1.79	0.143	0.107	2.30	3.10
	Out-of plane	0.221	0.219	5.46	3.54	0.012	0.033	70.9	68.8
Fully dense CFRP ablator[6]	In-plane	1.40	1.01	234	44.8	17.9	8.27	---	---
	Out-of plane	1.40	1.01	57.9	12.4	16.6	0.34	---	---

Table 4 The maximum surface and internal temperature of each specimens.

specimen	Heating rate (MW/m ²)	Surface temperature (°C)	Internal temperature (°C)	
			20 mm depth	30 mm depth
PCA1	1.8	2208	212	178
	3.2	2553	237	178
	6.0	2848	234	173
PCA2	1.8	2203	220	176
	3.2	2547	238	171
	6.0	2844	265	179
PCA3	1.8	2166	230	174
	3.2	2536	271	179
	6.0	2819	288	173

Fig. 6 Surface temperatures of PCA and TNPC under arc-jet wind tunnel.

Table 5 Surface recession rate of ablation materials.

specimen	Density (g/m ³)	Test condition	Heating time (s)	Heating rate (MW/m ²)	Stagnation pressure (kPa)	Surface recession rate (kg/m ² ·s)
PCA1	0.478	A	30	1.8	4.6	1.95
	0.478	B	30	3.2	13.0	3.72
	0.476	C	30	6.0	19.7	6.46
PCA2	0.478	A	30	1.8	4.6	1.84
	0.484	B	30	3.2	13.0	3.69
	0.481	C	30	6.0	19.7	6.29
PCA3	0.474	A	30	1.8	4.6	1.88
	0.477	B	30	3.2	13.0	3.50
	0.481	C	30	6.0	19.7	5.49
PICA[1]	0.254	---	11	5.1	21.3	5.9

4.2.2 Surface recession

In this study, surface recession rate was evaluated by,

$$m_1 = \rho \times l/t \quad (1)$$

where l is recession length at stagnation point, ρ is density of virgin ablator and t is heating time. Table 5 shows the surface recession rate of the specimen in each test. In test C, the surface recession rate of PCA is almost equal to that of PICA in the similar condition [1].

5. Discussion

5.1 Compressive test

5.1.1 Compressive strength of ablation materials

The compressive strength of PCA was maintained even after carbonization. This indicates that the structure of PCA is maintained. Fig. 8 shows the structure of virgin and charred PCA. No damage such as crack and delamination is observed in charred-PCA. However, it is known that conventional ablators such as PICA and CFRP are changed its structures due to carbonization. As mentioned above, PICA is mainly composed of short carbon fiber bound with a little resin and carbonaceous binders [3]. The resin shrinks and becomes brittle after heating because of carbonization. In case of CFRP, the crack and delamination at the interface between fibers and resin are induced during carbonization [7], and strength reduction occurs during re-entry. On other hand, PCA maintains its structure and strength after carbonization. This indicates that PCA is more mechanically stable compared with the conventional ablators.

Fig. 8 Microstructure of virgin and charred ablators.

5.2 Arc-jet wind tunnel test

As shown in Fig. 6, the difference of surface temperature increases in the test of higher heating rate. It is attributed to larger amount of pyrolysis gases generated in higher heating rate. Fig. 9 shows the cross section of PCA3 after tests. Three layers; white, brown and black layers are observed in every specimen. These layers correspond to charred layer, pyrolysis layer and virgin layer, respectively. The brown layer gets deeper in higher heating rate. This means that the larger amount of pyrolysis gases is generated in the higher heating rate.

Fig. 9 The cross section of PCA3 after the test.

Summary

In this study, we employed porous carbon material for new lightweight ablator. Compressive tests and arc-jet wind tunnel tests were carried out to evaluate the newly developed ablator. The result shows that the highest compressive strength was 26 MPa, which was 17 times higher than that of PICA in the in-plane direction. This strength was maintained even after carbonization. These mechanical characteristics suggested that PCA will be mechanically stable even in re-entry environment. In the arc-jet wind tunnel test, the surface temperature of the developed ablator was lower than that of the porous carbon preform. This result suggested that the developed ablator showed blocking effect by pyrolysis gases. The developed ablator also indicated thermal insulation performance. Although the maximum surface temperature is over 2000 °C, the internal temperature was in the range of 200 to 300 °C at 20 mm depth and about 170 °C at 30 mm depth. The recession rate was almost equal to existing ablator.

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